

Workshop Instructions: Assemble and measure your own solar photovoltaic module

ABOUT AURORA

The research project AURORA aims to engage students in energy communities through crowdfunding of solar photovoltaic installations at their universities and participation in discussions and hands-on activities related to solar energy.

This workshop was developed by Marta Victoria and Zhe Zhang, part of the AURORA team in Aarhus University, for participants to understand the basics of solar cells, assemble their own solar panels by soldering the solar cells and measure their power production outdoors.

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INSTRUCTIONS

Section A. Assembling your own solar photovoltaic module

In this workshop, you will assemble and solder a solar photovoltaic module consisting of multiple solar cells.

The use of gloves and goggles is optional but recommended. You can use tweezers to handle the tab wires. None of the materials are toxic but it is better to avoid grease from your fingers on the solar cells and tabs. The grease could reduce efficiency and make soldering difficult. **The solar cells are fragile, handle them with care to avoid breaking them.**

The tools that you will use can harm you, so pay attention and be careful when using them. Be extra careful with the soldering station.

You will need the elements depicted in Figures 1 and 2. All the materials are provided. You can use the glass frame provided to mount the solar panels. If you feel adventurous, you can also try to mount the solar cells on a different surface. In that case, make sure that the surface does not conduct electricity and that it is flat to avoid breaking the solar cells.

Figure 1. Elements required to assemble a solar PV module. (solar cells, tab wires, flux pen, soldering station, tweezers, tape, pliers)

Figure 2. Elements required to assemble a solar PV module: mounting frame for the precision-driller, glass frame, wooden table for soldering, wires (can be replaced by tab wires, more information on page 8).

The solar panel will comprise of multiple solar cells connected in series. To connect two solar cells in series we must connect the front side of one cell to the rear side of the other.

Start by making a drawing of the connections and the thin and wide tab wire that you need. See Figure 10 and 11 for the final configuration of the module.

Next, in preparation for connecting two solar cells in the same row, place the two cells next to each other, and measure out enough of the thin tab wire such that it covers both cells (Figure 3). The solar cells need to have a space of at least 5 mm between them.

Figure 3. Measuring the length of thin tab wire

For connecting to an external connection, measure and cut the thin tab wire such that it covers a solar cell and a few extra centimeters (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Measuring the length of thin tab wire.

Before soldering, clean the tab wire with the flux pen (Figure 5a) and clean the busbar in the solar cell with the flux pen (Figure 5b). Push the flux pen so that it starts to work.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Applying flux to tab wire (a) and solar cell bus bar (b).

Solder the thin tab wires to the front bus of the cells. Turn on the soldering station and select the maximum temperature (480 °C). Use the tweezers to position the tab wire on top of the front bus bar and solder by slowly passing the soldering iron over the solar cell. See Figure 6.

Be careful with the soldering iron to avoid burning you or your colleague.

The yellow sponge can be used to clean the tip of the soldering iron, if needed. Make sure it is damp with water before using.

Some tips for soldering:

- The thick soldering tip must be used for the solder. See Figure 7.
- Make sure that the solder tip is clear, use the yellow sponge and the metal sponge to clean it if needed. If the sponge is dry, pour some water on it.
- Move the soldering iron slowly to melt the tab wire. It should become shiny when melted. This is an indication of good soldering.
- When soldering, use a wooden surface, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 6. Soldering the thin tab to the front grid of the solar cell. You can watch a short video for this step [here](#).

Figure 7. The thick soldering tip for the solder is the bottom one.

After soldering the thin tab wire to the front side of the cells, you can solder the backside of the cells. Place one cell next to the other leaving a space of 3-5mm between them. It is a good idea to use tape to hold the two cells together while soldering. See Figure 8.

Figure 8. Tape is used to hold the two cells together before soldering the backside of the cells.

The solar cells are very fragile, and they can break easily. If this happens, you can use tape to “repair them”. See Figure 9. The cracks will reduce the efficiency of the solar cell, but if all the pieces are well connected to the front and rear metallic grids, the efficiency loss will be low.

Figure 9. Tape has been used to repair the solar cell.

Proceed with soldering the thin tab wires in all the cells. Measure and cut the necessary pieces of wide tab wire and complete connection of the solar cells in series. The following Figures show the front and back side of the solar cells connected in series (for 2 cells and 4 cells, respectively). It is recommended to use tape to fix the cells in their position in the glass before soldering the connections. See Figure 11.

Figure 10. Front side and back side of 2 solar cells connected in series.

Figure 11. Front side and back side of 4 solar cells connected in series. Tape has been used to fix the solar cell to the glass substrate.

The final step in the module assembly consists in soldering the external wires to the wide tabs to get the external positive and negative connections to the module.

Before soldering the connection, think how you want to get the wires out of the module. There are different options.

- (a) You can use the precision driller to make a hole in the frame
- (b) You can make a hole in the rear side of the module. In that case, you don't need to use the frame for your final module, you can use duct tape to hold the glass frame and the rear pane together.
- (c) You can use the tab wires

Once you have designed the connection, solder the red and black wires to the positive and negative connections of the solar module, respectively. You can use tin and the wiring terminal shown in Figure 12 to make a nice external connection.

Figure 12. Soldering the external connection

If you use the tab wires, here is how it will look like. This is easier as it does not requires drilling on the frames. The wires are “soft” enough to be bended and pressed into the frames.

Figure 13. Tab wires can be used to get the external positive and negative connections

Section B. Measuring your solar photovoltaic module

In section B, you will measure the current-voltage (I-V) curve of the solar photovoltaic module that you have assembled.

To get some practice, you will also measure the I-V curve of the small reference solar cell (Figure 14).

Write a report in which you include the following measured and calculated parameters.

- I-V curve (including plot).
- Short-circuit current, Open-circuit voltage, Fill factor and efficiency.
- Photocurrent density produced by the solar cell (in A/cm^2) assuming incident irradiance of $1000W/m^2$. How different is the value for the 4-cell module and the reference solar cell? (NB: given that the 4 cells are connected in series, how does this affect the value for their overall photocurrent density?)
- The irradiance and the ambient temperature of the measurement.
- The spectral distribution of the solar irradiance (measured with the spectroradiometer).
- Report those parameters for:
 - The small reference solar cell.
 - The 4-solar cell module that you have assembled.

Steps to measure the I-V curve.

The I-V curve should be measured under stable irradiance conditions. Try to do it under the real sun making sure that there are no shadows over the solar cell and the irradiance sensor.

Use the irradiance sensor (Figure 15) to determine the irradiance reaching the cell. Check the irradiance in between measurements to make sure that the irradiance level does not change significantly.

1. Connect the resistor box and the ammeter in series with the solar cell. Connect the voltmeter in parallel with the solar cell. See Appendix I for a review of the ammeter and voltmeter operation.
2. Start with the resistance box at zero (short circuit). Note the voltage and current. Increase the value of the resistors box and note the resistance, current and voltage in every step. Your final point should be with very high resistance (open circuit).
3. Plot the measurements and calculate the main parameters. [This link](#) provides a good suggestion on how to calculate the maximum power point of a solar cell based on experimental data.

Figure 14. Reference solar cell

Figure 15. Irradiance sensor

Figure 16. Elements required to measure a solar PV module (ammeter, voltmeter, resistors box)

Figure 17. Multimeter used as ammeter

Figure 18. Multimeter used as a voltmeter. For the millivolts scale remember to use the yellow button to select DC voltage.

Figure 19. Set-up to measure the short-circuit current of the reference solar cell.

Figure 20. Set-up to measure the IV curve of the reference solar cell.

Figure 21. Set-up to measure the IV curve of an individual solar cell (this measurement is optional).

Figure 22. Set-up to measure the IV curve of an individual solar cell in the lab (this measurement is only a second option if the outdoor measurement is not possible)

Figure 23. Set-up to measure the IV curve of the solar panel in the lab

Steps to measure the spectral distribution of the incident irradiation

We will use the Broadcom Qmini spectroradiometer to measure the spectral distribution of solar irradiance.

1. Download and install the Spectrometer Application Software WAVES from the web following [this link](#).

<https://docs.broadcom.com/docs/12398529>

2. Connect one side of the optical fiber to the spectroradiometer and the other side to the cosine corrector. A cosine corrector is an optical diffuser that couples to the fiber to collect signal from 180° field of view.

Remember to handle the spectroradiometer and the fiber carefully. Avoid hitting the spectroradiometer or pulling the fiber without unscrewing the thread.

3. Pointing the cosine corrector to the sky, measure and save the spectral distribution of the irradiance. Make a plot comparing the measured spectral distribution with the reference spectrum (AM1.5D). Discuss the main differences and what might be causing them.

Fig. 24. Spectrometer, optical fiber, and cosine corrector.

Fig. 25. Screenshot of the WAVES software showing a certain incident spectrum.

Appendix I. Measuring your solar photovoltaic module using a Multimeter

The **Voltmeter** is an instrument that measures the voltage difference between its terminals without perturbing the circuit.

Ideally, it drains no current (i.e., its internal resistance is infinite)

It has to be placed in parallel with the element to be measured

Figure 14. Parallel connection of a Voltmeter.

The **Ammeter** is an instrument that measures the current through its terminals without perturbing the circuit.

Ideally, it causes no voltage drop (i.e., its internal resistance is zero)

It has to be placed in series with the element to be measured.

Figure 15. Series connection of an Ammeter.

Figure 16. Multimeter used as ammeter

Figure 17. Multimeter used as a voltmeter. For the millivolts scale remember to use the yellow button to select DC voltage.

Figure 18. Set-up to measure the short-circuit current of the solar cell.